

THE CONCEPT OF DISTANCE LEARNING

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Annotation. The article examines the essence of distance learning, its state at the present stage. The concept of this knowledge acquisition system is discussed; the results of its application are analyzed.

Keywords: distance learning, internet forms of education, information space, and modern education system.

For many years, there has been a traditional form of education: attending classes and lectures, exams and an assessment system. However, in the last 10 years, and especially in the last year, due to globalization and the development of technology, distance learning has been successfully developing in parallel with the traditional form of education.

Distance learning has long attracted the attention of both teachers and trainees. Such training can take various forms depending on the organization and the training technologies used. Until recently, in our country, such training was mainly limited to the exchange of printed correspondence, occasional meetings of trainees with teachers during test and examination sessions. This is the so-called distance learning, which was widespread in all universities of the country, to a much lesser extent - in school education. In other countries, television and video recording capabilities were widely used for these purposes along with printed media. This is especially true for open universities. However, this practice has not been widely spread in the system of higher or secondary vocational education.

Distance learning, or rather, e-learning has taken a strong position in the modern training system, organically complementing full-time training and a variety of face-to-face trainings and courses. E-learning is actively used both in educational institutions and in enterprises, and in terms of popularity it will soon catch up with full-time. The world's leading analytical companies predict a great future for it and claim that the global market of distance learning systems is a source of great opportunities for sellers and investors. In the best higher educational institutions of the world, centers have been created that allow for distance learning with a corresponding diploma; corporate training centers of companies and government agencies are actively developing.(2)

Such a great interest in e-learning is explained quite simply. In the last decade, there have been significant changes in the labor market: the requirements for personnel have increased, information technologies have been

widely introduced into almost all spheres of activity, and the staff itself has become more mobile. Such changes made it necessary to create conditions for continuous, fast, flexible, and at the same time high-quality training, and since traditional training systems are not able to meet these needs, it was necessary to search for alternative systems.

Interest in distance learning has been formed for a long time. The correspondence form of obtaining knowledge was in demand in previous years, and now, in the era of rapid development of telecommunication technologies, distance learning is given a special attention. Teachers place great hopes on telecommunications and the world's Internet resources. One of the tasks of the education system in modern society is to provide everyone with free and open access to education throughout a person's life, taking into account their interests, abilities and needs. The state solved this task through the system of school, university education, a system of advanced training, including both full-time and correspondence forms of education. Distance learning in our country has rich traditions and successes. Tens of thousands of people who have received higher or second higher education have passed through the correspondence education system.

This form of distance learning has been and remains very popular. It allows you to take a training course in any discipline on the job. Additionally, this circumstance has always attracted and will continue to attract listeners on a bigger scale. The success of the correspondence form of education can be attributed to carefully developed teaching methods, tested over time and used for large groups of trainees. The distance learning system has accumulated a considerable experience in the development of methodological and educational materials, tasks for independent work, descriptions of laboratory work, and testing tasks. Of course, these developments should be successfully applied in new conditions. (3)

Distance learning as one of the forms of education is developing in the general direction of the scientific and technical revolution and informatization of public life. A new surge of interest in distance education arose against the background of the rapid development of telecommunication technologies, the emergence of the world information network - Internet. The pedagogical community began to place great hopes on these high-speed communication lines as a means of operational interaction between a teacher and a student outside the classroom. A computer and modem are becoming a familiar attribute of an office,

classroom, and apartment. In addition, this means that the potential audience of students increases dramatically.

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